

Fast and robust graph construction from KEGG metabolic and genomic data

Florent Cabret¹, Ronan Bocquillon¹, and Emmanuel Néron¹

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Abstract

The Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) enables the modelling of biological systems as integrated graphs, where directed metabolic networks capture reaction flows and undirected genomic graphs encode chromosomal proximity of enzyme coding genes. However, constructing these graphs at the scale of complete bacterial organisms remains challenging due to two limitations: web based API access is constrained by rate limits triggering temporary IP blocks, and existing tools are typically restricted to the scale of pathway analysis. Here we present a framework for the fast and robust construction of whole organism metabolic and genomic graphs from KEGG data. Our approach combines a concurrency model with proxy rotation to overcome web access bottlenecks, specialised parsers for tab-delimited and KGML formats, and an embedded analytical database for efficient storage. For graph construction, we introduce optimised methods that handle real world data complexities, including multiple genomic intervals per gene and uncertain boundary annotations. This enables, to the best of our knowledge, the first systematic construction of integrated graphs at the scale of complete bacterial genomes and entire metabolisms. By overcoming previous scalability barriers, our framework provides the foundation for applying advanced trail finding algorithms to reveal how metabolic function and genomic organisation co-evolve across the bacterial domain, moving beyond isolated pathways towards whole-organism comparative analysis.

Keywords: Systems Biology, Metabolic Networks and Pathways, Genome Bacterial, Data Collection, Graph Theory

¹Laboratoire d'Informatique Fondamentale et Appliquée de Tours, 64 Avenue Jean Portalis, 37200 Tours, France

Correspondence

ronan.bocquillon@univ-tours.fr, emmanuel.neron@univ-tours.fr

Introduction

The Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) was established in 1995 as a knowledge base for the systematic analysis of gene functions, with the ambitious goal of linking genomic information to higher order functional insights (Ogata et al., 1999). From its inception, KEGG has been structured around three core databases: the PATHWAY database for the graphical representation of biochemical pathways, the GENES database for consistently annotated gene catalogs from complete genomes, and the LIGAND database for chemical compounds and enzymes. By integrating genomic, chemical, and systemic functional information, KEGG serves as an indispensable reference for interpreting sequence data and understanding cellular processes, providing a foundational resource for applications ranging from the reconstruction of metabolic pathways to the analysis of gene expression profiles.

The utility of KEGG extends far beyond simple data retrieval. As demonstrated in studies such as Zaharia et al., 2019, KEGG data enables sophisticated integrative analyses that simultaneously consider metabolic pathways and genomic context. Their CoMetGeNe pipeline leverages KEGG's rich annotations to identify conserved metabolic and genomic patterns across multiple species, revealing how evolutionary pressures shape the organization of enzyme coding genes and their corresponding reactions. Such approaches exemplify the growing recognition that biological function emerges not from isolated components but from the complex interplay between metabolic networks and genomic architecture.

Accessing KEGG data programmatically has been facilitated through various software tools over the years. The KEGG API provides RESTful web services that allow automated retrieval of database entries, forming the backbone for numerous analysis pipelines. Early tools like KEGG-graph (Zhang and Wiemann, 2009) introduced graph based approaches to pathway analysis in R, capturing pathway topology for the first time. Specialized query systems such as IsoKEGG (Sultana et al., 2010, 2014) further expanded the possibilities by enabling logic based pathway queries using subgraph isomorphism, allowing researchers to retrieve pathways based on structural patterns. Integration tools like BiKEGG (Jamialahmadi et al., 2016) have bridged KEGG with other databases such as BiGG, facilitating cross database analyses. More recently, packages such as kegg_pull (Huckvale and Moseley, 2023) have improved accessibility through robust Python implementations that handle multiprocessing and fault tolerant retrieval. However, these tools share fundamental limitations inherent to web-based data access, namely rate limits that can result in temporary IP blocks, combined with a lack of built-in proxy support for large-scale concurrent requests. While kegg_pull's authors provide recommendations for sleep times to mitigate throttling, such measures necessarily trade speed for reliability, and the underlying constraints of operating within KEGG's API limits remain unchanged.

Despite these persistent constraints on data access, a particularly powerful paradigm that has emerged from KEGG's pathway representation is the modeling of biological systems as graphs. In this framework, metabolic pathways are represented as directed graphs where vertices correspond to enzymes (or reactions) and arcs represent substrate-product relationships between sequential reactions. Concurrently, genomic context can be modeled as an undirected graph where edges connect genes that are physically close on the chromosome. This dual graph representation (Zaharia et al., 2019) captures the fundamental insight that enzymes catalyzing successive reactions are often encoded by neighboring genes, reflecting evolutionary optimization of co-expression and functional coordination. The graph abstraction enables rigorous computational approaches: searching for maximum span trails in the metabolic graph whose vertex sets induce a single connected subgraph in the genomic graph reveals functionally coherent modules that transcend traditional operon definitions. These trails can subsequently be used for cross-species comparison, by grouping them based on shared reactions or conserved gene neighborhoods, to reconstruct phylogenetic relationships and trace the evolutionary history of metabolic pathways.

Despite the conceptual elegance of graph based representations, existing implementations have been constrained by computational complexity and scope. Early algorithms such as HNET (Zaharia et al., 2019) demonstrated the feasibility of identifying conserved metabolic genomic patterns but were limited to pathway by pathway analysis. Subsequent work by Ahmed Sidi,

2022; Ahmed Sidi et al., 2025 developed more efficient exact methods based on integer linear programming and constraint programming, demonstrating improved scalability on individual pathway instances. However, the \mathcal{NP} -hard complexity of the underlying problems imposed fundamental scalability limitations, preventing exact methods from extending beyond isolated pathway boundaries to encompass entire metabolic networks. Moreover, the reliance on KEGG's predefined pathway boundaries potentially fragments biologically meaningful patterns that span multiple pathways.

Recent algorithmic advances by Cabret et al., 2025 have improved this situation. Their binary integer programming model for finding maximum coverage trails in metabolic networks subject to genomic constraints achieves computational speedups of nearly 3000 times compared to previous approaches, allowing it to scale to networks with thousands of vertices. This development now makes it possible to begin systematic construction and analysis of integrated metabolic genomic graphs at the scale of complete bacterial genomes and full metabolisms. By considering all reactions and genes simultaneously, rather than focusing on individual pathways, this approach may help uncover broader organizational principles and evolutionary patterns that previous computational limitations made difficult to access. Additionally, their approach to generating biologically realistic benchmark instances through gamma-distributed degree sampling provides a way to create validation data that reflects true biological network properties. This offers an alternative to relying solely on simplified random graph models.

The convergence of rich KEGG data resources, sophisticated graph theoretic modeling frameworks, and increasingly more powerful algorithmic solvers creates an unprecedented opportunity to understand how metabolic function and genomic organization co-evolve across the bacterial domain. Realizing this opportunity, however, requires robust infrastructure for constructing integrated metabolic genomic graphs from KEGG data that can leverage these new computational capabilities. In this paper, we present a novel approach that addresses this need through two key contributions:

- Section 2 details a faster and more robust methodology for retrieving KEGG data, which overcomes the bottlenecks of web-based access through a concurrency model with proxy rotation and efficient parsing;
- then Section 3 introduces a graph construction framework operating at the scale of whole metabolisms and complete genomes, introducing optimized methods for building both directed metabolic graphs and undirected genomic graphs that handle real-world data complexities.

By moving beyond previous pathway-centric methods, this combined framework enables the application of advanced trail finding algorithms to complete bacterial systems.

Retrieving data from KEGG

To enable the scalable and robust construction of integrated metabolic genomic graphs at the scale of complete bacteria, our data retrieval pipeline is engineered as a cohesive system of four interdependent components. The process begins by programmatically contacting the KEGG REST API through a dedicated interface, after which the returned data, ranging from tab-delimited records to complex XML based KGML files, is parsed using specialized libraries tailored to each format. To overcome the inherent limitations of web-based access, including rate limits and the risk of temporary IP blocks, a sophisticated concurrency model manages thousands of parallel requests through a lock-free proxy rotation scheme, ensuring both speed and reliability. Finally, all retrieved and parsed data is efficiently stored in an embedded analytical database, where a carefully designed schema and bulk insertion strategy preserve referential integrity while maximizing throughput. Together, these elements form the foundation for acquiring the comprehensive, high quality datasets required for downstream graph analysis.

Concurrency model

The large number of independent web requests required to retrieve complete KEGG data for thousands of organisms makes concurrency essential. We therefore implement a thread pool to

106 manage these requests. Since most of the time in each request is spent waiting for a response
107 from the KEGG server, the pool is deliberately oversized, and we create 25 times the number of
108 logical processor threads. This over-subscription ensures that while some threads are blocked on
109 I/O, others can continue making progress, thereby maximising network utilisation.

110 A critical challenge when issuing many requests to the same public API is the risk of temporary
111 IP blocks. To mitigate this, we obtain before data retrieval begins a list of public proxies drawn
112 from [monosans/proxy-list](#), an hourly updated repository of freely available proxies scraped from
113 diverse sources and validated for reliability. Each proxy is then tested for reachability, requiring a
114 successful connection attempt to the KEGG website within 10 seconds and allowing up to three
115 retries. Proxies that pass this filter are stored in a global list alongside a flag indicating whether
116 they are currently in use and an optional timestamp of the last failure. This list is fixed for the
117 duration of the run and provides the pool of proxies used for all requests.

118 Access to this shared list must be efficient and must not become a bottleneck. We therefore
119 implement a lock-free proxy rotation scheme. Lock-free algorithms guarantee system-wide
120 progress even if individual threads are delayed, and they avoid the overhead of kernel-space
121 locking. Specifically we use the test and test-and-set idiom. A thread repeatedly reads the state
122 of a randomly chosen proxy; only if the proxy appears free does it attempt to claim it with an
123 atomic exchange. If the exchange succeeds, the thread proceeds to use the proxy. Should the
124 request later fail with an HTTP status of 400 or higher, which indicates a client or server error,
125 the proxy is marked as temporarily unavailable and a 5 second timeout is recorded. This timeout
126 value follows the recommendation of `kegg_pull` to avoid hammering a faulty proxy. Because
127 the entire selection loop uses only relaxed-order loads and a single acquire-release exchange,
128 contention on the proxy list is negligible.

129 Each request itself follows a robust retry policy. After a proxy has been acquired, the thread
130 issues a GET request with a generous one minute timeout. If the request times out or returns
131 an error status, it is retried up to three times. A failed request does not immediately discard the
132 proxy; instead the proxy is temporarily penalised (the 5 second timeout) so that other proxies can
133 be tried, while a faulty proxy is given time to recover.

134 Retrieved responses must be stored in a relational database while preserving referential
135 integrity. Because foreign keys must point to existing primary keys, we enforce a strict ordering
136 of insertions using the bulk synchronous parallel (BSP) model. The workflow is divided into
137 super-steps: first an organism is inserted, then all genes and positions, then enzyme annotations,
138 and finally the metabolic graph edges (see [Figure 1](#)). A barrier synchronises all worker threads
139 at the end of each super-step. The barrier itself is implemented with the low-level `atomic_wait`
140 and `notify_all` primitives. Threads that finish early start the next super-step up to the point of
141 committing to the database; if the remaining threads have not yet reached the barrier, they first
142 spin briefly before finally parking on the atomic flag. This hybrid approach avoids excessive
143 context switching when the last thread is expected to arrive quickly, while still allowing long
144 waits to block efficiently. This design guarantees that no thread ever tries to insert a row that
145 references a still missing primary key.

146 To further reduce contention, each thread maintains its own database connection in thread-
147 local storage. Instead of issuing individual INSERT statements (which would require repeated
148 round trips and serialisation), threads accumulate rows in memory and commit them in bulk
149 transactions. This approach minimises lock contention on the database and significantly cuts the
150 number of inter-thread synchronisation events. Only when a barrier is reached must the threads
151 ensure that all their buffered writes have been applied; the atomic wait barrier provides exactly
152 that guarantee.

153 **Contacting the API**

154 To programmatically access the KEGG REST API, we are using [libcurl](#), a free and portable
155 client-side URL transfer library. It supports a wide range of protocols including HTTPS, which is
156 required for all of the endpoints, and provides robust features such as persistent connections,
157 thread safety, and comprehensive error handling. Its ability to seamlessly handle HTTP and
158 SOCKS proxies, including those requiring authentication, is particularly valuable in institutional

159 and high-performance computing environments where direct external access may be restricted.
160 By leveraging libcurl, our workflow can reliably retrieve genomic, pathway, and chemical data
161 from KEGG while automatically routing traffic through necessary proxy servers, ensuring both
162 reproducibility and resilience in diverse network settings.

163 Parsing CSV and XML

164 The KEGG API returns data in several distinct formats depending on the operation performed.
165 Most operations including list, find, conv, and link return tab-delimited text that can be parsed
166 line by line, while pathway data retrieved via the get operation with the kgml option is provided in
167 the XML-based KGML (KEGG Markup Language) format. These two structural paradigms require
168 different parsing strategies: the former demands efficient, type-safe handling of flat records, while
169 the latter requires navigating hierarchical relationships between pathway elements. To address
170 these requirements, we employ two specialized C++ libraries. For tab-delimited responses, we
171 leverage the PEG based parser combinator library [lexy](#) to construct declarative grammars that
172 map directly onto data structures. For KGML, we utilize the DOM interface provided by [pugixml](#)
173 to traverse and extract pathway components.

174 Parsing Expression Grammars (PEGs) provide a formal and unambiguous method for describing
175 machine oriented syntax using ordered choice operators (Ford, 2004). This paradigm was notably
176 adopted by the CPython interpreter in Python 3.9 (PEP 617) to lift the LL(1) restrictions and
177 simplify grammar maintenance. The practical advantages of this approach are now being demon-
178 strated in production database systems, with the recently released DuckDB v1.5.0 adopting a PEG
179 based parser to enable runtime extensibility and deliver significantly improved error messages
180 and auto-completion. This validation in a high-performance setting reinforces our choice of a
181 PEG based solution for the KEGG parsing task. To process KEGG's tab-delimited outputs, we im-
182 plement this approach using [lexy](#), a C++ parser combinator library. Its expressive domain-specific
183 language embeds grammars within the code, mirroring the structure of handwritten recursive
184 descent parsers while providing explicit control over backtracking through branch conditions.
185 This design avoids the performance pitfalls common in traditional PEG implementations. By
186 constructing specialized grammars, we ensure type-safe and zero-copy parsing, complete with
187 robust error recovery to handle the irregular formatting sometimes found in biological data dumps.

188 To process KGML outputs, we employ [pugixml](#), a lightweight and high performance XML
189 parsing library. This format encodes pathway information in a hierarchical structure that defines
190 elements such as genes, compounds, reactions, and their relations. The library's DOM inter-
191 face provides intuitive traversal methods, enabling efficient navigation of the KGML structure
192 and ensuring reliable data extraction for subsequent analysis through the retrieval of pathway
193 components with minimal overhead.

194 Database management system

195 [DuckDB](#) is a fast analytical, in-process, open-source and portable database system. Following
196 the paradigm popularized by SQLite, it operates embedded within a host application, eliminating
197 external dependencies and the overhead of inter-process communication. Its architecture is
198 specifically optimized for Online Analytical Processing (OLAP) workloads through a columnar-
199 vectorized query execution engine, which processes data in large batches rather than row-by-row
200 to accelerate complex aggregations and joins on massive datasets. This combination of embedded
201 simplicity and analytical performance makes DuckDB particularly well suited for efficient data
202 analysis within the application itself. To support this analysis, the database is structured according
203 to the entity-relationship model illustrated in [Figure 1](#). Such a unified storage could also benefit
204 tools like KEGG spider (Antonov et al., 2008), which builds a global gene metabolic network by
205 integrating all the pathways, enabling the interpretation of gene lists in a pathway-free context.
206 Rather than treating each pathway as an independent unit, it constructs a unified network where
207 genes are connected if their associated reactions share common compounds. It then infers
208 network models from an input gene list by progressively connecting genes at increasing distances
209 and assesses the statistical significance of these models through Monte Carlo simulations. This

210 approach offers an alternative to the directed metabolic graph construction presented later in
 211 this paper.

Figure 1 – Entity-relationship diagram of the database

212 Numerical experiments

213 Retrieving complete KEGG data for 1000 bacterial organisms with our approach requires
 214 approximately one hour of total runtime, with a variance of about ± 15 minutes attributable to
 215 the heterogeneous performance of public proxies (since all threads must synchronise at each
 216 super-step, a slower proxy can delay every worker). In practice, the number of proxies can be
 217 reduced to avoid placing an excessive load on the KEGG server. For smaller analyses involving
 218 at most 100 organisms, the parallel portion of the workload is substantially reduced. Amdahl's
 219 law (Amdahl, 1967) then predicts that the fixed overheads, notably the two minutes needed for
 220 initial proxy filtering, dominate the total time, making the concurrent strategy less beneficial than
 221 a simpler sequential retrieval. In terms of data quality, our pipeline issues more API calls than the
 222 method of Zaharia et al., 2019 because it fetches complete, fine-grained data for every organism
 223 instead of relying on global association tables. The additional calls are the price paid for obtaining
 224 precise reaction-enzyme associations and handling complex genomic annotations, which the
 225 earlier approach approximated or omitted.

226

Construction of the graphs

227 The core of the analysis framework lies in constructing two complementary graph representa-
 228 tions from the retrieved KEGG data: a directed metabolic graph capturing the flow of substrates
 229 and products between reactions, and an undirected genomic graph encoding the chromosomal
 230 proximity of the associated enzyme-coding genes. These constructions follow the foundational

231 concepts introduced by Zaharia et al., 2019, which enable the integrated analysis of metabolic
232 and genomic organization. To achieve the necessary performance for organism scale analysis, we
233 have developed optimized variants of these foundational constructions. The following subsections
234 describe each graph construction in detail, using side by side comparison with the original
235 methods to highlight how our approach overcomes previous scalability limitations.

236 Metabolic graph

237 The metabolic graph is a directed graph that models the flow of metabolites through a
238 sequence of reactions. In Zaharia et al., 2019, its construction begins by representing both
239 reactions and chemical compounds as nodes in a bipartite graph. Directed edges are placed from
240 substrate compounds to the reactions they participate in, and from each reaction to its product
241 compounds. For reversible reactions, edges are added in both directions to preserve biochemical
242 reversibility. The final directed graph is obtained by projecting this bipartite structure onto the
243 set of reaction nodes. In this projection, two reactions become connected by a directed arc if a
244 product of the first reaction serves as a substrate for the second. This results in a pathway centric
245 directed graph where arcs trace feasible metabolic sequences, abstracting away the underlying
246 compounds.

247 In this work, we adopt a more efficient construction that bypasses the explicit bipartite graph
248 and its projection. Instead, we maintain two hash maps: one that associates each compound with
249 the set of reactions that produce it, and another that associates each compound with the set of
250 reactions that consume it. For every compound, we then iterate over all producer-consumer pairs
251 and directly add a directed arc from the producer to the consumer whenever the product of the
252 former serves as a substrate of the latter. This approach eliminates the storage of intermediate
253 bipartite edges and the overhead of a separate projection step. During arc creation, we also
254 query the enzymes associated with each reaction and discard any reaction that lacks an enzyme
255 annotation, ensuring that only reactions with genomic support are retained in the final graph.
256 The resulting directed graph retains the same biochemical interpretation, arcs represent feasible
257 metabolic transitions, but is constructed in a single pass with reduced memory footprint and
258 lower time complexity, making it particularly suitable for large-scale metabolic network analysis.

259 Genomic graph

260 The genomic graph is an undirected graph that captures the spatial proximity of genes en-
261 coding the enzymes of the corresponding reactions. Zaharia et al., 2019 first build this graph
262 by linking consecutive genes on each chromosome, forming a linear chain. For circular bacterial
263 chromosomes, an additional edge connects the first and last gene to correctly reflect the circular
264 topology. By default, the graph is constructed separately for genes on the forward and reverse
265 strands, reflecting the biological observation that functionally related genes tend to reside on the
266 same strand. This behavior can be modified to consider genes on both strands together when
267 a more permissive neighborhood definition is desired. To allow for gaps between functionally
268 related genes, the shortest path distances in this initial gene graph are computed. If two genes
269 are separated by at most a specified number δ of intermediate genes along the chromosome, an
270 edge is added directly between them (typically, $\delta \leq 3$). Reactions are then mapped to the genes
271 that encode their enzymes. Two reactions are linked by an undirected edge precisely when their
272 associated genes are neighbors in the graph. This genomic graph thus encodes the condition
273 that the genes of a metabolic trail must lie in a genomically coherent cluster.

274 In this work, we employ an Order Statistic Tree using as the base data structure the Logarithmic
275 Binary Search Tree introduced by Roura, 2001. In this structure, the size of the subtree stored
276 at each node serves the dual purpose of both maintaining the balancing property and enabling
277 efficient rank queries. Each gene can be associated with multiple genomic intervals due to the
278 presence of introns or uncertainties arising from high-throughput sequencing errors. In our
279 database schema (see Figure 1), a gene can thus be associated with several position entries.
280 Other complications include entries where the stop value is missing, in which case we set it equal
281 to the start value. Additionally, a flag field, which we currently ignore, might indicate that the
282 true start or stop lies outside the reported values.

283 The positions of all genes are inserted into the tree ordered by their start value. The data
284 structure provides logarithmic time rank queries, which we use to compute genomic distances
285 efficiently. For a given pair of genes, we first compute a new interval spanning from the smallest
286 start value to the largest stop value among all intervals belonging to that gene. If these new
287 intervals don't intersect, the genomic distance between the two genes is simply the distance
288 between them. This value can be obtained directly using rank queries on the tree without
289 examining individual intervals.

290 When they overlap, a more detailed analysis is required. We apply a sweep line algorithm
291 on the sorted list of all interval endpoints belonging to the two genes. The algorithm maintains
292 two pointers, each initially pointing to the first interval of the respective gene. At each step, it
293 compares the current intervals: if they intersect, the distance is zero; otherwise, it advances the
294 pointer corresponding to the interval with the smaller start value. This process continues until
295 either an intersection is found or all intervals have been processed, yielding the minimal distance
296 between any two positions belonging to the two genes. By leveraging the Order Statistic Tree for
297 initial sorting and span checks, and the sweep line for overlapping cases, we achieve an efficient
298 and accurate computation of gene neighbourhood distances even in the presence of multiple
299 position intervals per gene.

300 It is worth noting that the genes encoding enzymes represent only a small subset of all coding
301 genes in a genome. This specificity makes the construction of the genomic graph more computa-
302 tionally manageable and focuses the analysis on biologically relevant functional units. Compared
303 to the approach of Zaharia et al., 2019, which does not account for the complexities introduced by
304 multiple intervals per gene, missing stop values, or flag attributes indicating uncertain boundaries,
305 our method is designed to handle these real-world data imperfections robustly. By efficiently
306 computing distances between genes even in the presence of such complications, our approach
307 provides a reliable foundation for downstream analyses. This capability could prove particularly
308 useful for trail comparison if the need for less strict genomic constraints were to arise, thereby
309 supporting scalable whole genome analyses.

310 To go further, the genomic graph, which captures chromosomal proximity between enzyme-
311 coding genes, could be refined by integrating spatial proximity data derived from chromosome
312 conformation capture techniques such as Hi-C. The contact matrix used by Gao et al., 2024
313 provides genome-wide interaction frequencies between genomic loci, revealing that genes
314 physically close in the three-dimensional space of the nucleoid are more likely to be functionally
315 associated, even when they are far apart on the linear chromosome. By incorporating these spatial
316 interaction frequencies as additional edges in the genomic graph, the resulting network could
317 better reflect the functional organisation of the genome, complementing our method. Moreover,
318 manual annotations remain valuable for correcting annotation errors, resolving ambiguous gene
319 boundaries, or incorporating experimentally validated interactions that may not be captured by
320 high-throughput data.

321 Numerical experiments

322 To illustrate the scalability of our graph construction pipeline (see Table 1), we built metabolic
323 and genomic graphs for six bacterial species with diverse number of reactions: the reduced
324 genome of the secondary endosymbiont of *Trabutina mannipara* (senm), the *Blochmannia* en-
325 dosymbiont of *Camponotus (Colobopsis) obliquus* 757 (ben), the porcine pathogen *Glaesserella*
326 *parasuis* SH03 (hpas), the marine bacteria *Vibrio campbellii* ATCC BAA-1116 (vac), the model organ-
327 ism *Escherichia coli* K-12 MG1655 (eco), and the opportunistic pathogen *Klebsiella grimontii* (kgr).
328 Construction of both graphs from the retrieved KEGG data scales with the organism complexity
329 and consistently takes under 30 seconds. While the six species studied here span a wide range
330 of reaction counts, the average across all bacteria is 946. The experiments confirm that finding a
331 maximum span trail in these graphs (i.e., at the scale of a complete bacterial organism) is tractable,
332 even if it requires more time than expected. In contrast, Cabret et al., 2025 solve this same
333 problem on a set of biologically realistic synthetic graphs of 1060 vertices in less than 3 seconds
334 on average, and they obtain longer trails (36 reactions on average). These discrepancies highlight

335 the computational challenge of the underlying combinatorial problem, as well as the difficulties
 336 to create an accurate model of synthetic graphs.

Bacteria name		senm	ben	hpas	vca	eco	kgr
Number of reactions		26	340	647	958	1130	1269
Metabolic graph	order	17	309	594	863	1019	1161
	size	22	538	1484	2737	3578	4071
Genomic graph	size	26	1377	2091	2489	2620	2899
Construction time (s)		0.3	4	9	15	22	26
Maximum span trail		5	10	25	18	12	12
Resolution time (s)		0.05	2	7	29	83	89

Table 1 – Statistics for different bacterial species

337 Conclusion

338 We have presented a framework for constructing integrated metabolic and genomic graphs
 339 from KEGG data at the scale of complete bacterial organisms. Our approach addresses the
 340 bottlenecks of web-based data retrieval through a concurrency model with proxy rotation. Our
 341 graph construction pipeline leverages two specialized data structures: hash maps for efficient
 342 metabolic graph assembly and order statistic trees for genomic proximity computations. To the
 343 best of our knowledge, this enables the first systematic construction of whole organism graphs
 344 that were previously limited to pathway by pathway analysis.

345 With these organism scale graphs and the trails they support, the next challenge becomes
 346 comparative analysis across species. Zaharia et al., 2019 provided an elegant method for identify-
 347 ing conserved patterns. However, their approach reintroduces a segregation between reactions
 348 and genes during comparison: trails are treated as reaction sets, temporarily decoupling the
 349 metabolic and genomic dimensions that the model itself integrates.

350 The availability of whole organism graphs now calls for comparison methods that preserve this
 351 duality. We need approaches that identify conserved substructures simultaneously in both meta-
 352 bolic and genomic dimensions. Such methods would reveal not only which reaction sequences
 353 persist across evolution, but also how their underlying genomic organization is maintained or rear-
 354 ranged. Developing these methods represents the next frontier in understanding the co-evolution
 355 of metabolism and genome architecture across the bacterial domain.

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358 Conflict of interest disclosure

359 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of
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361 Data, script, code, and supplementary information availability

362 Data, script and codes are available online (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19025626>;
 363 Cabret et al., 2026).

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